

GAME EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

*N. Rakhmatova*¹

Abstract:

The article is devoted to innovative educational technologies using the example of the use of didactic games in the lessons of Russian as a foreign language. Particular attention is paid to varieties of language and speech games. The author focuses on creative and role-playing games in the lessons of Russian as a foreign language.

Key words: innovative technologies, didactic games, types of games, educational technologies

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Introduction. Play as a method of learning and transferring social experience has been used since ancient times. In modern schools, play activities are used by teachers:

- as an independent technology for mastering a concept, topic, and even a section of an academic subject;
- as an element of a more general technology;
- as a lesson or part of it (introduction, control);
- as a technology for extracurricular activities.

G.K. Selevko gives the following definition of gaming technology: “this is a type of activity in situations aimed at recreating and assimilating social experience, in which self-government of behavior is formed and improved” [1]. The concept of “game innovative technologies” includes a fairly broad group of methods and techniques for organizing the pedagogical process in the form of various pedagogical games. Unlike games in general, a didactic game has an essential feature - a clearly defined learning goal and a corresponding pedagogical result, which can be justified, identified explicitly and characterized by an educational-cognitive orientation [2]. The place and role of gaming technology in the educational process, the combination of game and learning elements largely depend on the teacher’s understanding of the functions of didactic games. Of particular note are the following:

1. Entertaining. Strategic game, organization of a cultural space of entertainment for the student, in which he goes from entertainment to development.
2. Communicative. A game is a communicative activity that allows the student to enter the real world of human communications.
3. Self-realization. The game allows the student to assert himself and identify his shortcomings.
4. Diagnostic. The game provides an opportunity for the teacher to diagnose the student’s acquired knowledge (intellectual, creative, emotional, etc.).

¹*Rakhmatova Nigina Islomovna, Senior Lecturer at Tashkent branch of the Russian State Pedagogical University named after Herzen*

5. Interethnic communication: the game allows the student to assimilate universal human values and the culture of representatives of other nationalities.

Materials and Methods: The use of methods for performing creative tasks in lessons creates psychologically comfortable conditions for students: the task is perceived not as a test, but as a game, and ensures the emotional stability of the student.

Voluntary nature, the opportunity to choose and elements of competition, satisfaction of needs, self-affirmation and self-realization provide motivation for the student's gaming activity. Educational games are a very effective means of mastering a lesson.

One of the most important problems of teaching the Russian language is teaching oral speech, which creates conditions for revealing the communicative function of the language and makes it possible to bring the learning process closer to the conditions of real learning, which increases motivation for learning the Russian language. Involving students in oral communication can be successfully carried out during gaming activities. Games can be divided into two main groups:

1. Didactic games, which include grammatical, lexical, phonetic and spelling games that contribute to the development of students' speech skills. Unlike games in general, didactic games have a significant difference. In the process of didactic games, a connection is made with a specific educational goal; it can be repeated, interrupted and started again.

The main difference between didactic games and other educational games is that

There is no set pattern of behavior in the game, and the participant himself chooses a possible variant of verbal interaction and evaluates the result of its implementation. The game, as a rule, is of an adversarial, competitive nature. A student, entering into relationships with playing partners, evaluates his strength not only in comparison with other players. The game allows him to objectively assess his capabilities.

2. Creative role-playing games are one of the ways to teach foreign languages. Role play is a very flexible learning activity with a wide range of possibilities for variety and imagination. Role-playing games make extensive use of various communication techniques, thereby developing language fluency, interaction in the classroom and increasing motivation.

Role-playing games can be divided into the following types:

1) Short-term role-playing game, which is the simplest and fastest type of game, lasting from 10 to 30 minutes. It can be based on text or dialogue. An example of this game can be presented in the form of an interview.

2) A full-fledged role-playing game in which students are provided with a description of the situation and their roles. The duration of this type of game takes on average one or two lessons. As an example, consider verbal role-playing games. This type of game occurs through verbal interaction between participants describing the actions of their game characters.

3) Long-term role-playing games are a more complex type of games, lasting from a series of lessons or more. When preparing long-term role-playing games, the teacher must provide students with handouts and provide students with a clear definition of the game situation. The goal of this game is to force students to act together, solving problems and puzzles that the teacher sets for them in the process of exploring the world of the game.

Role-playing improves students' speaking skills in any situation because almost all of the class time in role-playing is spent on speaking practice.

Conclusion. Thus, gaming technologies occupy an important place in the educational process. The wide range of role-playing games allows them to be used in any part of the curriculum [3]. At the same time, they are a very useful tool that makes learning the Russian language interesting and memorable. Role-playing games provide a positive emotional state for students and a communicative focus of the lesson. Gaming activities are the most attractive for schoolchildren, which affects the effectiveness of teaching the Russian language. Games have a positive effect on the formation of students' cognitive interests and contribute to the conscious development of the Russian language. They promote the development of such qualities as independence, initiative, and the ability to work in a team. Students work actively, enthusiastically, help each other, listen carefully to their comrades, and the teacher only manages their learning activities.

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